

ISic2773

I.Sicily inscription 2773

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

volcanic

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lipara

Place of origin (modern)

Lipari

Provenance

Contrada Diana

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lipari, Museo Archeologico Regionale Eoliano "Luigi Bernabò Brea",
inventory 13459

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Ἀρισ[τ][---]

2. νος[---]

Apparatus

text of Meligunis Lipára XII

Bernabò Brea and Cavalier: Ἀρισ[τίω]

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645170

PHI 334208

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum*

graecum. At 45.1381.9

Bernabò Brea, L., Cavalier, M., Campagna, L. 2003. Meligunìs Lipára. XII. Le iscrizioni lapidarie greche e latine delle isole eolie. Palermo. At 106

Bernabò Brea, L., Cavalier, M. 1994. Meligunis Lipara VII. Lipari. Contrada Diana. Scavo XXXVI in proprietà Zagami (1975-1984). Palermo. At no.9 pl.123

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